

Development of a novel tool to simulate solar thermal cogeneration plants using small-capacity tower plants

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ABSTRACT

Water scarcity and sustainable energy production are critical global challenges. This study addresses these issues by developing a simulation tool for solar thermal cogeneration plants that integrate a micro-gas turbine with a central receiver solar power plant with multi-effect desalination units. This integration can produce both electricity and freshwater without energy penalties. The simulation tool, implemented using Python, has been applied to a coastal location in Cyprus. Results indicate a 20 % higher output of electricity and freshwater during summer compared to winter, with a maximum solar fraction of 33 % achieved in July. This approach demonstrates the potential for efficient, small-scale renewable energy solutions to simultaneously meet water and energy needs.

1. Introduction

Water scarcity is considered one of the main problems for the immediate future worldwide. One of the Sustainable Development Goals defined by the United Nations, Goal 6, aims to ensure water availability, sustainable management, and sanitation for all inhabitants of the planet [1]. The use of desalination systems to obtain fresh water is presented as a reliable solution to mitigate the availability problem. According to the International Desalination Association (IDA), the global contracted capacity already reached 100 million m³/d [2], and it is expected to continue growing exponentially due to existing issues such as climate change, population growth, increasing industrialization and pollution of existing resources. Most of the large-scale desalination capacity installed today uses Reverse Osmosis (RO) technology while the rest is based on thermal energy-powered distillation processes, being Multi-stage Flash (MSF) and Multi-effect Distillation (MED) the most widely implemented. Among these latter ones, MED has predominated in recent years due to its higher efficiency compared to MSF. The main disadvantage of desalination is its energy-intensive nature, which can transform the water scarcity issue into an energy and environmental problem. The use of fossil fuels to desalinate water has a considerable impact on CO₂ emissions (for instance, a RO plant emits around 2 kg of CO₂ per m³ of desalinated water [3]), which can jeopardize the sustainability of this

sector. It is clear that replacing these fuels with renewable energies is necessary to achieve the decarbonization of the desalination industry. Among the different renewable energy sources, solar energy is the one with the highest potential and the most predominant in water-stressed regions. It is therefore logical to use it to produce fresh water through desalination. Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) is the preferred option for large-scale solar desalination, as this technology allows to achieve higher capacity factors due to the cheaper thermal storage systems (i.e. the ones based on molten salts) in comparison with the batteries in the case of Photovoltaics (PV). Among the different CSP technologies, parabolic trough collectors are the most established and widely installed nowadays [4]. However, the CSP plants based on Central Receiver (CR) technology have gained maturity and popularity in recent years and currently represent the majority of plants under development. Among CR-CSP plants, those involving a Brayton cycle offer major advantages over Rankine CSP technologies, such as higher efficiency, simplicity and reliability. Additionally, when combined with thermal desalination for joint freshwater and electricity production (CSP + D schemes), Rankine power cycles experience a significant reduction in efficiency making the concept economically unviable. This efficiency reduction has been proven in some of the papers published by Palenzuela et al., who evaluated deeply the integration of MED systems into the Rankine power cycle of a CSP plant. In their first works, they did a techno-economic analysis of CSP + MED plants at the design point [5,6], in which they

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Nomenclature*Symbols*

A	Area, m ²
A_s	Absorber surface area, m ²
c_p	Air heat capacity at constant pressure, J/kg·K
c_v	Air heat capacity at constant volume, J/kg·K
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiance, W/m ²
G	Air mass flow per unit receiver area, kg/(m ² ·s)
GOR	Gain Output Ratio, –
h	Enthalpy, J/kg
I_b	Power incident on the receiver, W
L	Length, m
LHV	Lower Heating Value, J/kg
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate, kg/s
p	Pressure, bar
T, t	Temperature, °C
MTD	Minimum Temperature Difference, °C
N	Number of effects
PP	Pinch Point, °C
PR	Compression ratio, –
q	Volumetric flow rate, m ³ /day
\dot{Q}	Heat rate, kW
RR	Recovery Ratio, %
TC	Thermocompressor location, –
U	Convective heat transfer coefficient, W/(m ² ·K)
v	Velocity, m/s
\dot{W}	Electric power, kW
X	Seawater salinity, ppm
x	Auxiliar variable

Subscripts/superscripts

a	Air
amb	Ambient
b or B	Brine
c	Condenser
C	Condensate
cob	Combustor
com	Compressor
d, D	Distillate
dsh	Desuperheater
e	Electric
E	Evaporator
exh	Exhaust
f	Fuel
F	Feed
FB	Flash-box
g	Glass
gas	Sum of fuel and air
L	Location
m	Cavity air

mot	Motive steam
n	Nominal
$preh$	Preheater
rec	Receiver
reg	Regenerator
s	Absorber or Steam
SG	Steam generator
sh	Superheated
suc	Suction vapor
sw	Seawater
T	Total
tur	Turbine
V	Vapor
w	Water
'	Variable after demister
"	Variable in the flash box

Acronyms/abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
$CAES$	Compressed Air Energy Storage
$CCPP$	Combined Cycle Power Plant
CR	Central Receiver
CSP	Concentrating Solar Power
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiance
EES	Engineering Equation Solver
FMI	Functional Mock-up Interface
FMU	Functional Mock-up Units
GOR	Gain Output Ratio
IDA	International Desalination Association
$LCOE$	Levelized Cost of Electricity
$LCOW$	Levelized Cost of Water
LHV	Lower Heating Value
MED	Multi-effect Distillation
$NREL$	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
$NRMSD$	Normalized Root-Mean-Square Deviation
PSA	Plataforma Solar de Almería
PV	Photovoltaics
RO	Reverse Osmosis
SG	Steam Generator
$SolarPILOT$	Solar Power Tower Integrated Layout and Optimization Tool
TMY	Typical Meteorological Year
TVC	Thermal Vapor Compression

Greek letters

γ	Ratio of specific heats
η	Efficiency
α	Absorptivity or vapor fraction
τ	Transmissivity
σ	Stefan-Boltzman constant
λ	Enthalpy of vaporization

found that the efficiency of the power block decreased by around 19 % with respect to a conventional Rankine power cycle. It had an impact on the costs, being the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) up to 20 % higher than in conventional parabolic trough CSP plants without desalination. In other work carried out more recently, they addressed the evaluation in terms of annual operation [7], in which they found that the penalty in the electricity generation integrating a MED unit in the power cycle was around 10 %. Some authors have proposed schemes in MED + Rankine CSP plants aiming to reduce this penalty by maximizing the electricity and water productions at part load conditions. Ortega-Delgado et al [8,9] evaluated the best coupling arrangements and

operational strategies of MED-TVC units integrated into a Rankine power cycle of a commercial parabolic trough CSP plant to maximize the water and electricity productions as a function of the electricity demand and the position of the thermocompressor. Others have proposed schemes in Rankine CR-CSP plants that increase the efficiency of the power block, for instance by the use of the waste heat from the molten salts storage system for an Organic Rankine power cycle [10]. However, CR-CSP plants with Brayton cycles present a greater opportunity for the integration of thermal desalination systems. In the case of Rankine power cycles, any change in the CSP plant (either the thermal storage system or the power cycle) would mean a penalty in the thermal

efficiency and the need of extra heat exchangers in addition to the use of heat recovery system. In the case of the Brayton power cycles, all the waste heat from the power block that would otherwise be dumped into the environment can be further exploited by the thermal desalination system, such as MED, without any efficiency penalty.

Up to now, most of the works found in the literature related to the joint freshwater and electricity production by CR-CSP plants based on Brayton cycles deal with supercritical CO₂ (sCO₂). Out of these works, there are some ones that do not involve a direct integration between the waste heat of the sCO₂ Brayton cycle and the desalination plant. This is the case of Sharan et al. [11], who included two demineralized water tanks that stored the waste heat from the power cycle and then were used to preheat the feed seawater and to provide the main heat source for the MED first effect. The study was performed for different locations and Yanbu (Saudi Arabia) obtained the cheapest cost of the distillate and electricity generation, producing 115 MW_e and 4720 m³/d, with a thermal efficiency of 48 %. Another work is the one carried out by Kouta et al. [12]. They did an economic analysis of a CR-CSP plant based on sCO₂ Brayton cycle with thermal storage, combined with a MED with thermal vapor compression (MED-TVC). In this case, the energy source required by the MED-TVC unit was taken from the thermal storage, and the waste heat of the sCO₂ cycle was used to preheat the feed seawater. The average LCOE and leveled cost of water (LCOW) obtained were between 0.08 \$/kWh and 1.05 \$/m³. Wang et al. [13] performed the design and operational model of a CSP + D system consisting of a CR-CSP plant with sCO₂ Brayton cycle and a MSF desalination unit. In this case, the heat needed for the MSF unit was taken from one of the molten salt tanks that composed the thermal storage system. The results obtained from the operational model showed that the efficiency of the power cycle was 36.6 % and the electric power and freshwater daily output of the CSP + D system 50.1 MW_e and 4050.8 t, respectively.

Other works considered the use of waste heat from the sCO₂ Brayton cycle in a CR-CSP plant to drive the MED unit. Yuan et al. [14] studied the effects of the change in some parameters of the sCO₂ Brayton cycle and the MED on the power cycle efficiency and freshwater production. The main findings were that an increase of 150 °C in the turbine inlet temperature led to an increase in the cycle efficiency of 6.51 % while freshwater production remained unchanged. On the other hand, an increase of 9 MPa in the maximum pressure of the sCO₂ Brayton cycle had hardly any effect on the efficiency, while water yield increased from 512 m³/day to 566 m³/day. Maia et al. [15] evaluated the same MED integration with sCO₂-CR-CSP, but they analyzed five different locations in Brazil. They found that the most suitable locations in terms of performance and water production were those with the lowest latitude due to the lower variation in the annual solar irradiation. In the case of Omar et al. [16], they did a thermo-economic analysis to evaluate the potential of integrating several MED systems (with different number of effects) into a sCO₂-CR-CSP plant, aiming to increase the waste heat recovery to more than 50 %, compared with 25 % reported in other works previously in the literature. The study was done for several locations, both coastline and inland, accounting for the pipe investment cost for the latter. The results found that the most optimal MED system in terms of waste heat recovery was the one with four effects, which could recover up to 57 % of the total waste heat. The LCOW was the lowest for the CSP + D plant located close to the coast, with results between 0.11 and 0.18 USD/m³ (compared with the cogeneration plant located inland whose LCOW was 5.6 – 7.1 USD/m³ due to the high pipeline investment cost). Other authors have considered a combined cycle together with the sCO₂ one, such as Khademi et al. [17] who added an organic Rankine cycle to the sCO₂ CR-CSP-desalination plant to further increase the efficiency. The resulting exergy efficiency was 61.8 %, with an optimum number of effects in the MED unit of 9.

As can be proven by the rapid growth in research, supercritical CO₂ thermodynamic cycles are one of the most promising applications and future research trends [18]. However, it has been also reported that this technology has several challenges, such as those ones related to the

bearings of the turbomachinery [19], corrosion [20], lack of cycle's compactness [21] and to the optimal operation and control, which probably have avoided their deployment at commercial scale so far [22].

Among the air Brayton cycles, those involving micro-gas turbines in CR-CSP plants (known as solar mini-power tower) can be a potential solution to the current sCO₂ Brayton cycles for small-scale, flexible and distributed power generation. They are modular and offer low costs of building new transmission and distribution lines, making them an interesting option for rural areas (off-grid production) [23]. In addition, unlike the sCO₂ cycles, air Brayton cycles do not have cooling needs which usually causes a critical water consumption problem, especially in arid areas [24]. Additionally, the most attractive advantage of these cycles in the CSP + D context is that the high amount of exhaust heat that cannot be further exploited by a combined cycle (because it would be unfeasible for a steam turbine due to the small size required) provides the possibility of integrating thermal desalination technologies with no penalty in power plant efficiency.

Research on solar tower with air turbine and thermal desalination is very scarce. In the case of Ghasemiasl et al. [25], they considered an existing fossil Combined Cycle Power Plant (CCPP) located in Iran to become a hybrid fossil-solar multigeneration system with the aim to improve its performance and to reduce the environmental impact. For this approach, they proposed a solar tower but without the air Brayton cycle. In this case, a molten salt thermal storage was integrated into the CCPP, being the waste heat used to drive an Organic Rankine Cycle to produce electricity (used for H₂ production) and to drive a steam turbine whose steam extraction was used to produce freshwater through a MED-TVC unit. They did a 4E (Energy, Exergy, Environmental and Exergo-economic) analysis in which they obtained that the exergy and thermal efficiency improved by 16 – 27 % and 25 – 36 %, respectively, depending on the operation modes. In the case of Alirahmi et al. [26], they evaluated an innovative combination of Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES) with a solar tower and a MED-TVC unit from a thermodynamic and economic point of view. In this scheme, there is not an air Brayton cycle coupled with the solar tower but the heat collected in the central receiver is stored in a hot tank to be used during peak demand periods to increase the air temperature leaving the CAES before entering the gas turbine. The waste heat remaining after the expansion in the turbine is then used for the production of fresh water in the MED-TVC unit. They developed the model for the entire system and used the location of San Francisco (United States of America) as a case study, which yielded a total potable water production of 226,782 m³ and energy generation of 27,551 MWh in one year with a payback period of 2.65 years. None of the previous works considers the entire integration of a thermal desalination system with the waste heat of a micro-gas turbine coupled with a solar tower (solar mini-power tower). Therefore, the main novelty and contribution of the authors is the development of a novel and powerful simulation tool that allows evaluating the annual performance of CR-CSP + D systems consisting on solar mini-power towers plus MED-TVC units. The solar micro-gas turbine plant is based on the same configuration as AORA SOLAR technology. The AORA solar power plant, a demonstration facility at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), uses a solar tower with a heliostat field to concentrate sunlight onto a receiver, heating air to drive a micro-turbine for electricity generation. It operates efficiently even during cloudy periods or at night by integrating a hybrid system that can use alternative fuels like natural gas or biogas, ensuring a continuous power supply, see [27,28] for further details.

All the components of the CR-CSP + MED-TVC plant have been modelled based on physical equations, and then the models have been connected to each other to develop the simulation tool. Such a tool allows performing annual simulations just by selecting the geographical coordinates of the location of the proposed system and its potential has been proven by its application to a coastal location in Chipre, obtaining interesting results of the annual freshwater and electricity production.

2. Methods

The methods followed in this analysis include a detailed description of the system and all its components, identifying the key elements and their interactions. After that, a comprehensive mathematical model of the system at component level is presented. Finally, a case study is simulated with the developed tool to show its potential.

2.1. System description

The system consists of a small-capacity CSP plant utilizing central receiver technology with a pressurized air-based power Brayton cycle, also known as solar mini-power tower, following the same configuration as AORA SOLAR plant [27,28]. The system includes the integration of a MED-TVC unit for desalination application, which is powered by the exhaust gas of the turbine (see Fig. 1).

The gas cycle comprises an air compressor, a combustor, and a turbine, together with a regenerator to recover part of the heat from the

exhaust gas. The process can be described as follows (see the thermodynamic cycle in Fig. 2): initially, the pressure and temperature of the air (p_{amb}, T_{amb}) is increased in the compressor (p_{com}, T_{com}) and subsequently is heated in the regenerator (p_{com}, T_{reg}) using part of the heat from the turbine's exhaust gas. Then, two scenarios may appear: if solar irradiance is present (daylight time, clear sky), the compressed air is directed to the receiver of the solar tower where it is heated up (p_{com}, T_{rec}). Additional heat may be required to reach the nominal temperature of the air in the turbine. In this case, the compressed air goes to the combustor, where it is mixed with fuel and burned (p_{com}, T_{cob}). The second scenario occurs when there is no solar irradiance (nighttime, clouds, etc.), and the compressed air (p_{com}, T_{rec}) is sent directly to the combustor through a three-way valve. Afterwards, the compressed air (or air-fuel mixing) (p_{com}, T_{cob}) enters the turbine where it is expanded (p_{tur}, T_{tur}), producing mechanical energy that is eventually converted into electricity in an electric generator.

The exiting gases (p_{tur}, T_{exh}) from the turbine are used to drive the desalination process based on MED-TVC technology. For that, there is an

Fig. 1. Scheme of the CR-CSP plant with the MED-TVC unit.

Fig. 2. Thermodynamic cycle of a gas turbine.

economizer and a steam generator that generate the steam, which is then compressed in a thermocompressor and used as heating steam in the first effect of the desalination unit. The condensed steam leaving the first effect is then returned to the steam generator passing firstly through the economizer. The MED-TVC unit takes seawater and produces fresh water by consecutive evaporation–condensation processes through a series of effects or stages. Part of the entering seawater is used as cooling water for the vapor condensation in the last effect, and it leaves the desalination process returning to the sea together with the brine that is the other sub-product of the process. The exhaust gases from the economizer are released into the atmosphere.

2.2. Modeling and simulation

An overview of the simulator structure is given in Fig. 3. Different software environments have been used to model each component of the system and they all have been integrated using the Python programming language [29]. The simulator has been developed as a web application, in which the graphical user interface has been designed using Dash [30], an open-source Python framework for building data visualization interfaces. In addition, the following Python libraries have been used in the simulator: the Pandas library [31], which has been used to manage time series data, NumPy [32], used to perform data format transformations and Plotly [33], used to create various kinds of graphs.

The main components of the simulator (as shown in Fig. 3) are weather data, solar field model, receiver & cycle model and the MED-TVC model. The modeling and simulation of each one is described in detail in the following subsections.

2.2.1. Weather data

The weather data required to perform the simulations are the hourly Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI), ambient temperature and pressure. They can be supplied by a comma-separated values file or directly downloaded from PVGIS [34], an open internet tool for the assessment of solar resources. The solar radiation data available at PVGIS is a combination of databases: PVGIS-SARAH2 and PVGIS-SARAH (Europe, Africa, Central Asia), PVGIS-NSRDB (Americas) and PVGIS-ERA5 (Nordic countries above 60 N and the rest of the world).

The developed simulation tool features a graphical user interface that facilitates the acquisition of essential weather data for conducting the simulation (DNI, ambient temperature, and pressure). Users simply need to select a specific location, and the tool automatically retrieves the data for the Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) from the PVGIS based on the chosen location’s latitude and longitude. There are several methods to select a location: by searching for an address, selecting a point on a map, which then provides an address, or by directly introducing the latitude and longitude coordinates. Should an address be provided, the tool employs the GeoPy geocoding Python library, which, in turn, utilizes the Nominatim tool to fetch the latitude and longitude from OpenStreetMap [35].

The simulator recovers the TMY data from PVGIS using the Requests Python library [36], through PVGIS’s web-based Application Programming Interface (API) non-interactive service [37]. Then, the simulator shows a summary of the downloaded weather data together with hourly graphs for the DNI, ambient temperature and pressure.

Fig. 3. Simulator structure.

2.2.2. Solar field model

The heliostat solar field model has been created using the Solar Power Tower Integrated Layout and Optimization Tool (SolarPILOT) [38], which was developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL). SolarPILOT models the heliostat field (see the model parameters in Table 1) based on the solar field’s layout (depicted in Fig. 4). The model of the heliostat field includes a control system that reflects and concentrates incoming solar radiation onto the receiver. For this purpose, the required geometrical data of the tower and the receiver (parameters listed in Table 2) were established according to the real plant, AORA SOLAR. Additionally, an atmospheric model (parameters listed in Table 3) is also required. SolarPILOT’s default values were employed in this instance. The model generates an output that maps the distribution of concentrated solar flux on the receiver.

The solar field model has been exported as an SPT file in SolarPILOT, which is then imported into Python using the CoPylot library [39] (as can be seen in Fig. 3). This library provides access to all SolarPILOT’s capabilities to generate and characterize CR-CSP systems seamlessly through Python. The model provides the solar flux distribution over the receiver according to the hourly weather data, the parameters of the heliostat field model, the ones of the tower and receiver model, and the ones of the atmospheric model (notice that this one was the default one considered by SolarPILOT).

For the case of the solar flux distribution from the solar field, a study was first performed to determine the minimum grid discretization to reduce the simulation time but without committing an error greater than 1 % in the total power over the receiver. Fig. 5 shows the results of this discretization study. The x-axis represents the grid resolution, whereas the y-axis represents the simulation time in seconds for each hour of the year. The orange line represents the total power over the receiver

Table 1
Heliostat field model parameters.

Parameter	Value
Heliostat name	AORA SOLAR
Focusing type	At slant
Canting method	On-axis at slant
Number of heliostats	45
Heliostat height and width	4 m, 4 m
Heliostat reflectivity	94 %
Soiling factor	95 %
Number of heliostat facets (X, Y)	2, 2
Facets’ gap (X, Y)	5 mm, 5 mm
Ratio of reflective area to profile	100 %
Elevation and azimuth pointing error	0 rad, 0 rad
Surface slope error (X, Y)	1.53 mrad, 1.53 mrad
Reflected beam error (X, Y)	1.53 mrad, 1.53 mrad

(values in the left y-axis), whereas the blue line (values in the right y-axis) is the simulation time for a common laptop (CPU with 4 cores) and the green line for a supercomputer (252 cores in total). The study revealed that a grid resolution of 250 × 250 is enough to obtain a solar flux distribution with a total power over the receiver with a deviation lower than 1 % compared to a grid resolution of 1000 × 1000. Notice that the 250 × 250 grid calculations for an entire year require 2 h on the common laptop and 12 min on the supercomputer, whereas the 1000 × 1000 grid calculations require 1.4 days on the common laptop and 2.5 h on the supercomputer.

2.2.3. Power cycle model

This section describes the models of each one of the main elements of the power cycle: compressor, regenerator, solar receiver, combustor, and gas turbine (see Fig. 1) together with the thermodynamic properties of the fluids considered in the power cycle (air and combustion gas). All these models have been implemented in the Modelica language [40] using the Dymola tool [41]. The models were exported as Functional Mock-up Units (FMUs), files with FMU extension, using the Functional

Table 2
Tower and receiver model parameters.

Parameter	Value
Receiver name	AORA SOLAR
Aperture type	Rectangular
Receiver height and width	708 mm, 708 mm
Tower optical height	35 m
Flux profile type	Uniform
Acceptance angle (X, Y)	180°, 180°
Peak flux	1000 kW/m ²
Heliostat aim point method	Image size priority
Flux simulation model	Hermite (analytical)
Receiver discretization	250 × 250
Min. Image offset from receiver edge (X, Y)	2, 2

Table 3
Atmospheric model parameters.

Parameter	Value
Sun shape model	Pillbox sun
Sun shape angular extent	4.65 rad
Insolation model	Weather data
Atmospheric attenuation model	DELSOL3 clear day
Attenuation coefficient 0	0.006789
Attenuation coefficient 1	0.1045
Attenuation coefficient 2	-0.017
Attenuation coefficient 3	0.002845

Fig. 4. Solar field layout in SolarPILOT.

Fig. 5. Results of the receiver grid discretization study.

Fig. 6. Solar receiver heat transfer physical principles.

Mock-up Interface (FMI) standard [42] (it is a standard for model exchange and co-simulation between different modeling and simulation tools), and then imported into Python by the FMPy library [43] (see Fig. 3).

2.2.3.1. *Compressor.* The compressor model is given by Eq. (1) to (5) [44,45] and it simulates the inlet air temperature, pressure, mass flow rate and compressor exit temperature, pressure, and power.

Table 4
Solar receiver model parameters.

Parameter	Description	Value	Units	Reference
A_s	Absorber surface area	0.7	m ²	Engineering documentation
α_g	Quartz glass absorptivity	3	%	[48]
τ_g	Quartz glass transmissivity	95	%	[48]
U_g	Convective heat transfer coefficient	150	W/(m ² ·K)	[27]
σ	Stefan-Boltzmann cte.	5.60·10 ⁻⁸	W/(m ² ·K ⁴)	

Table 5
Combustor model parameters.

Parameter	Description	Value	Units	Reference
η_{tur}	Turbine efficiency	84.8	%	[52]
PR_{tur}	Expansion ratio	4.5	–	[52]
$\dot{m}_{a,n}$	Nominal air flow rate	0.72	kg/s	[28]
$\dot{m}_{f,n}$	Nominal fuel flow rate	0.0066	kg/s	[53]

$$\gamma_{com} = \frac{c_{p,com}}{c_{v,com}} \quad (1)$$

$$x_{com} = \left(PR_{com} \frac{\dot{m}_a}{\dot{m}_{a,n}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma_{com}-1}{\gamma_{com}}} \quad (2)$$

$$T_{com} = T_{amb} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{x_{com}-1}{\eta_{com}} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$p_{com} = p_{amb} \cdot PR_{com} \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{W}_{com} = \dot{m}_a \cdot c_{p,com} \cdot (T_{com} - T_{amb}) \quad (5)$$

The inputs of the model are: T_{amb} , which is the ambient temperature, in °C, p_{amb} , which is the ambient pressure, in bar, and \dot{m}_a , which is the air mass flow rate, in kg/s. The outputs are: T_{com} , which is the compressor outlet air temperature, in °C, p_{com} , which is the compressor outlet air pressure, in bar, and \dot{W}_{com} , which is the compressor outlet air power, in kW. Finally, the internal variables (those ones calculated by the equations or from thermodynamic properties) are: $c_{p,com}$, which is the compressor air heat capacity at constant pressure, in J/kg·K, $c_{v,com}$, which is the compressor air heat capacity at constant volume, in J/kg·K, γ_{com} (–), the ratio of specific heats, and x_{com} (–), which is a variable introduced to simplify Eq. (3).

Regarding the model parameters, their description and values considered have been the following ones: η_{com} (–) is the compressor efficiency and takes a value of 78.6 % [44], PR_{com} (–) is the compression ratio and takes a value of 4.5 [44] and $\dot{m}_{a,n}$ is the nominal air flow rate that takes a value of 0.72 kg/s [28].

2.2.3.2. *Regenerator.* The heat regenerator model is given by Eq. (6) and (7) which define the regenerator outlet temperature (T_{reg} , in °C) and exhaust gas temperature (T_{exh} , in °C) (see Fig. 2) [46].

Fig. 7. Air and fuel specific heat capacities at constant pressure and volume.

Fig. 8. Scheme of the steam generator and MED plant.

Table 6
Some equations of the MED-TVC design model [8].

Equation	Eq.	Comment
$\dot{m}_s \lambda_s + \dot{m}_s \bar{c}_{p,s,sh} (T_{s,sh} - T_s) + \dot{m}_{F1} h_{pre2} + \dot{m}_{FB1} h_{V1}'' = (1 - \alpha_1) \dot{m}_{T1} h_{V1}' + \alpha_1 \dot{m}_{T1} h_{C1} + \dot{m}_{B1} h_{B1}$	(20)	Energy balance in the first effect
$\dot{Q}_1 = \dot{m}_{F1} \bar{c}_{p1} (T_1 - t_{preh1}) + \dot{m}_{D1} \lambda_{V1} = A_{e1} U_{e1} (T_s - T_1)$	(21)	Heat transfer equation in the first evaporator
$\left(\dot{m}_F - \sum_{k=i+1}^N \dot{m}_{F,k} \right) \bar{c}_{p,preh1} (t_{preh1} - t_{preh2}) = \alpha_1 \dot{m}_{T1} \lambda_{V1}' + \alpha_1 \dot{m}_{T1} \bar{c}_{p,BPE1} (T_{V1}' - T_{vsat1})$	(22)	Energy balance in preheater 1
$(\dot{m}_{suc} + \dot{m}_{dsh}) h_{sc} + \alpha_1 \dot{m}_{T1} h_{C1}' = \dot{m}_{C1} h_{C1}'' + \dot{m}_{FB1} h_{V1}''$	(23)	Energy balance in flash box 1
$\dot{m}_{a,preh,in} h_{a,preh,in} + \dot{m}_{w,preh,in} h_{w,preh,in} = \dot{m}_{a,preh,out} h_{a,preh,out} + \dot{m}_{w,preh,out} h_{w,preh,out}$	(24)	Energy balance in the preheater of steam generator
$\dot{m}_{a,SG,in} h_{a,SG,in} + \dot{m}_{w,SG,in} h_{w,SG,in} = \dot{m}_{a,SG,out} h_{a,SG,out} + \dot{m}_{w,SG,out} h_{w,SG,out}$	(25)	Energy balance in the steam generator

$$T_{reg} = T_{com} \frac{c_{p,com}}{c_{p,reg}} + \frac{\eta_{reg}}{c_{p,reg}} \cdot (T_{tur} \cdot c_{p,tur} - T_{com} \cdot c_{p,com}) \quad (6)$$

$$T_{exh} = T_{tur} \frac{c_{p,tur}}{c_{p,exh}} + \frac{\eta_{reg}}{c_{p,exh}} \cdot (T_{tur} \cdot c_{p,tur} - T_{com} \cdot c_{p,com}) \quad (7)$$

where T_{com} and T_{turb} are the compressor outlet air temperature and the turbine outlet gas temperature, in °C, respectively, and they are both input of the model; $c_{p,com}$, $c_{p,reg}$ and $c_{p,tur}$, in J/(kg·K), are the compressor

air heat capacity at constant pressure, the regenerator gas heat capacity at constant pressure and the turbine gas heat capacity at constant pressure, respectively, and they are all internal variables. Finally, $\eta_{reg}(-)$, is the regenerator efficiency and it is a parameter of the model, whose value of 78 % has been considered [47].

2.2.3.3. *Solar receiver.* The pressurized closed volumetric solar receiver (see Fig. 6) [27] has a quartz glass window where the solar radiation passes through and heats up the absorber which in turn heats the working fluid (which is combustion gas). Dashed red arrows represent thermal radiation, solid orange arrows denote the solar beam, and the inlet and outlet air are represented by solid light grey and red arrows, respectively. Equations of the model are numbered from (8) to (12) [27]. Eq. (8) represents the energy balance in the quartz glass window, Eqs. (9) to (11) account for the energy balance in the cavity and Eq. (12) is used to determine the absorber temperature.

$$I_b \cdot \alpha_g + \sigma \cdot (T_{amb}^4 + T_s^4 - 2 \cdot T_g^4) = U_g \cdot (T_g - T_{reg}) \quad (8)$$

$$G = \frac{\dot{m}_a}{A_s} \quad (9)$$

$$G = \frac{I_b \cdot \tau_g + \sigma (T_g^4 - T_s^4)}{h_{rec} - h_m} \quad (10)$$

$$h_m - h_{rec} = \frac{U_g \cdot (T_g - T_{reg})}{G} \quad (11)$$

Table 7

Values of the input variables for the design MED-TVC model (based on authors' expertise except indicated).

Variable	Symbol	Value	Unit	Reference
MED-TVC				
Number of effects	N	10	–	
Thermocompressor location	TC_L	Last effect	–	
Heating steam temperature	T_s	70	°C	
Inlet seawater salinity	$X_{sw,in}$	35,000	ppm	
Inlet seawater salinity temperature	$T_{sw,in}$	25	°C	
Distillate outlet temperature	T_d	25	°C	
Outlet brine temperature	T_b	40	°C	
Recovery ratio	RR	37.5	%	
Condenser minimum temperature difference	MTD_c	3	°C	
First preheater minimum temperature difference	$MTD_{preh,1}$	3	°C	
Motive steam pressure	p_{mot}	5	bar	
Brine output pressure	p_b	2	bar	[56]
Distillate output pressure	p_d	2	bar	[56]
Inlet seawater pressure	$p_{sw,in}$	1	bar	
Seawater pressure loss from intake	$\Delta p_{sw,intake}$	6.5	bar	[57]
Distance of the plant to the sea	L	2778	m	[57]
Pump efficiency	η_{pump}	0.7	–	
Pump electric efficiency	$\eta_{pump,e}$	0.9	–	
Brine velocity	v_b	1	m/s	
Control panel power consumption		1.5	kW	[58]
Chemical dose power consumption		0.5	kW	[58]
Steam generator				
Inlet air temperature to SG	$T_{a,SG,in}$	270	°C	
Inlet air pressure to SG	$p_{a,SG,in}$	1.13	bar	
Inlet air mass flow rate to SG	$\dot{m}_{a,SG,in}$	0.7266	kg/s	
Pinch point ⁽¹⁾ in SG	PP_{SG}	5	°C	

⁽¹⁾ $PP_{SG} = T_{a,SG,out} - T_{w,SG,in}$.

Table 8

Input summary for the model.

Input	Min	Max	Sum
DNI (W/m ²)	0.00	922.32	1.79×10^6
Ambient temperature (°C)	3.84	30.96	–
Ambient pressure (kPa)	92.15	95.05	–

$$T_s = \frac{T_{reg} + T_m}{2} \quad (12)$$

The input variables of this model are: the power incident on the receiver (I_b), in W; the ambient temperature (T_{amb}), in °C; the regenerator outlet air temperature (T_{reg}), in °C and the air mass flow rate (\dot{m}_a), in kg/s. The internal variables are: the mass flux (G), which denotes the air mass flow per unit receiver area, in kg/(m²·s); the absorber temperature (T_s), in °C; the glass temperature (T_g), in °C; the cavity air temperature (T_m), in °C; the regenerator outlet air enthalpy (h_{reg}), in J/kg; the cavity air enthalpy (h_m), in J/kg and the receiver outlet air enthalpy (h_{rec}), in J/kg. The output from the model is the receiver outlet air temperature (T_{rec}), in °C. The model parameters (together with their corresponding values) are described in Table 4.

2.2.3.4. Combustor. For the model of the combustor, the output combustor temperature is calculated by Equation (13), [44].

$$T_{cob} = T_{rec} + \frac{\eta_{cob} \cdot LHV \cdot \dot{m}_f}{c_{p,cob} \cdot \dot{m}_{gas}} \quad (13)$$

Where T_{rec} (receiver temperature, in °C), \dot{m}_a (air mass flow rate, in kg/s) and \dot{m}_f (fuel mass flow rate, in kg/s) are the inputs of the model; \dot{m}_{gas} is the sum of the fuel and air mass flow rate, in kg/s; $c_{p,cob}$ (combustor gas heat capacity at constant pressure, in J/(kg·K)) is an internal variable of the model and T_{cob} (combustor temperature, in °C) is an output of the model. The parameters of the model, η_{cob} (combustor efficiency) and LHV (Lower Heating Value) have been considered at 90 % [49] and 47,141 kJ/kg [50], respectively.

2.2.3.5. Gas turbine. Eqs. (14) to (19) define the gas turbine model considering an isentropic process and the turbine efficiency [51]. Eq. (14) represents the ratio of specific heats. Eq. (15) was introduced to simplify Eq. (16) which defines the turbine temperature, and it is derived from the turbine irreversible adiabatic efficiency, considering an isentropic process. Eq. (17) defines the turbine pressure from the compressor pressure and the turbine expansion ratio, and Eqs. (18) and (19) determine the turbine and net power.

$$\gamma_{tur} = \frac{c_{p,tur}}{c_{v,tur}} \quad (14)$$

$$x_{tur} = \left(PR_{tur} \cdot \frac{\dot{m}_f + \dot{m}_a}{\dot{m}_{f,n} + \dot{m}_{a,n}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma_{tur}-1}{\gamma_{tur}}} \quad (15)$$

$$T_{tur} = T_{cob} \cdot \left(1 - \eta_{tur} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{x_{tur}} \right) \right) \quad (16)$$

$$p_{tur} = \frac{p_{com}}{PR_{tur}} \quad (17)$$

$$\dot{W}_{tur} = \left(\dot{m}_a + \dot{m}_f \right) \cdot c_{p,tur} \cdot (T_{cob} - T_{tur}) \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{W}_{net} = \dot{W}_{tur} - \dot{W}_{com} \quad (19)$$

The inputs of this model are: T_{cob} , p_{com} , \dot{m}_a , \dot{m}_f and \dot{W}_{com} . The internal variables are: $c_{p,tur}$, which is the turbine air capacity at constant pressure, in J/(kg·K), $c_{v,tur}$, which is the turbine heat capacity at constant volume, in J/(kg·K), γ_{tur} , which is ratio of specific heats; x_{tur} , which is an auxiliary variable introduced to simplify Eq. (16). Finally, the output variables of the model are: T_{tur} ; p_{tur} , which is the turbine pressure, in bar; \dot{W}_{tur} , which is the turbine power, in kW and \dot{W}_{net} , which is the net power, in kW. The parameters of the model are shown in Table 5.

2.2.3.6. Thermodynamic properties of fluids. Air heat capacities at constant pressure and volume are calculated from a detailed dry air model [54], which considers an ideal gas of several substances where the mole fractions are fixed: N₂ (78.08 %), O₂ (20.95 %), CO₂ (0.94 %) and Ar (0.03 %). As can be seen in Fig. 7, heat capacities depend only on temperature and are valid in the following range: [-73 °C, 5000 °C]. Regarding the combustion gas heat capacities, they have also been calculated considering an ideal gas of several substances with the following fixed mole fractions [55]: N₂ (75.80 %), O₂ (15.51 %), CO₂ (2.92 %), H₂O (4.86 %) and Ar (0.91 %). As in the case of air, they only depend on temperature (see [55]) and are valid in the same range.

2.2.4. Model of the thermal vapor compression multi-effect distillation unit

The desalination unit integrated into the CR-CSP plant is a parallel/cross MED-TVC plant whose layout is shown in Fig. 8. In this configuration, an equal amount of feedwater enters each effect, where it partially evaporates producing vapor and brine (un-evaporated water). The brine generated in each effect is mixed with the brine of the next effect, while the vapor is used to promote a new evaporation–condensation process in the next effect. The model is based in

Fig. 9. DNI for the selected location, data obtained from PVGIS [34].

Table 9
Results summary.

Mass Flow rates (kg/s)	Min	Max	Average	Sum
Ambient air + fuel	0.7200	0.7266	0.7232	22,705.92 ton
Fuel	0.00	0.066	0.032	191.15 ton
Temperatures (°C)	Min	Max	Average	Sum
Compressor	191.77	236.25	214.25	–
Regenerator	388.99	592.84	465.52	–
Receiver	294.66	844.93	442.26	–
Combustor	652.84	951.12	762.90	–
Turbine	421.77	659.27	509.25	–
Exhaust	235.87	325.72	273.62	–
Pressures (kPa)	Min	Max	Average	Sum
Compressor	414.70	427.73	421.30	–
Turbine	109.13	112.56	110.87	–
Power (kW)	Min	Max	Average	Sum (MW)
Compressor	136.68	149.92	143.37	1260
Turbine	186.16	248.71	208.74	1830
Net	38.22	110.46	65.37	572.64
Receiver	0.00	401.71	57.45	503.26
Solar	0.00	92.01	22.77	199.48
Fuel	11.86	90.36	42.60	373.16
MED-TVC	3.61	4.85	4.10	35.92
MED-TVC	Min	Max	Average	Sum
Distillate (m ³ /day)	32.70	47.44	40.19	14,671.01 m ³
GOR	9.05	13.47	11.52	–
Performance	Min	Max	Average	Sum
Solar ratio (%)	0.00	87.80	22.93	–
Fuel ratio (%)	12.20	100	77.07	–
CO ₂ emissions (kg/h)	4.40	33.52	15.80	138.44 ton
Fuel usage (L/h)	19.42	70.29	54.55	477.87 kl

mass and energy balances on each component, together with the heat transfer equations of the heat exchangers. Firstly, a design model has been used to find out the areas of the evaporators, preheaters, and final condenser. Such a model was already developed and implemented in Engineering Equation Solver (EES) by some of the authors of this paper

Fig. 10. Monthly net power and distillate production.

[8]. The most representative equations of the model are presented in Table 6 and the values of the main inputs of such model are presented in Table 7. Variables are defined in the nomenclature, while inputs considered are assumed except where otherwise indicated, based on usual data from MED commercial plants. There are two additional components that have been modelled within this work to integrate the MED-TVC unit into the power cycle: an economizer, which is used to preheat the water, and a steam generator, which drives the production of the motive steam. Once the surface areas are obtained from the design model, an operational model (implemented in EES software), also developed by the authors of this paper in [9], has been used considering the areas as inputs to perform simulations at different operating conditions.

Note that a value of 5 bar has been considered for the motive steam pressure at design conditions. It has resulted from a previous sensitivity analysis performed by the authors of this paper in [59], from which the best results in terms of freshwater production were obtained. Also, 5 °C of difference between the air temperature at the outlet of the steam generator and the water temperature at the inlet of the steam generator has been assumed as a standard value for this type of heat exchangers.

To model the integration of the MED unit with the rest of the CR-CSP plant in Python, a multi-variable polynomial regression has been obtained from the results delivered by performing simulations with the operational model. The inputs of the polynomial regression and the range of variation were the inlet temperature of the air (T_{ext}), between 235 and 325 °C; the total mass flow rate (fuel plus air) (\dot{m}_{gas}), between 0.72 and 0.7266 kg/s; and the air pressure (P_{tur}), between 1.10 and 1.13 bar. The outputs from the polynomial regression were the Gain Output Ratio (GOR) and the freshwater production (in m³/day). Polynomial

Fig. 11. Monthly solar and fuel fractions.

regression was developed considering 185 operational points and the regression coefficients for the three outputs were obtained using the tool MultiPolyRegress in MATLAB software. The resulting equation together with their coefficients are listed in Appendix A.

On the other hand, the power consumption of the MED has been correlated as a function of the temperature, pressure and mass flow rate of the entering air to the steam generator. The data used for obtaining this correlation are also presented in Appendix A. The fit was evaluated using the Normalized Root-Mean-Square Deviation (NRMSD). The results proved good accuracy and concordance with the ESS model, with the advantage of significantly reducing the computational time for the simulation.

2.3. Case study

The developed simulation tool has been used to calculate the annual electricity and water productions in the Proteas CSP facility at The Cyprus Institute in Pentakomo (Cyprus), which is approximately 160 m from the sea and has the following geographical coordinates: 34°42'25.2"N, 33°15'37.3"E.

As mentioned before, the only model inputs are DNI, ambient temperature and pressure, which are obtained from the TMY generated by PVGIS for the selected location. In the case of Pentakomo, these inputs are the ones depicted in Table 8. Fig. 9 shows the DNI of this location for the whole year.

3. Results

Table 9 presents a comprehensive summary of the results obtained from the annual simulation in terms of minimum, maximum, average, and cumulative totals for key parameters such as mass flow rates, temperatures, pressures, and power output, alongside the performance metrics of the MED-TVC and the power cycle. Note that the simulator's adaptability allows for its application to any selected location, as long as the model variables remain within a comparable range to those outlined in Table 9 for each respective variable.

Fig. 10 illustrates the monthly net power output and distillate production, while Fig. 11 outlines the proportions of solar energy and fuel used each month. As can be observed, July and August were the best months, producing around 20 % more electricity and freshwater compared with winter months (such as February). In addition, the freshwater and electricity produced during summer months took place with a higher solar fraction than in winter months (33 % in July against 11 % in December). It is important to highlight that the solar fraction could be further increased in case energy storage was included. Currently, there is no energy storage for Brayton cycles at commercial stage but under development. This is the case of a Compressed Air Energy Storage integrated into an air Brayton cycle that is going to be proven at pilot scale within a recent European project, ASTERIX-

CAESAR [60] in which the authors of this paper are working.

Fig. 12 presents a comparative analysis over time of the results obtained for two distinct weeks: one during winter (4th – 10th February) and another in summer (7th – 13th July). In turn, Fig. 12 has five sub-figures: a to e. Fig. 12a shows ambient temperature (red line) and temperatures for the components of the Brayton cycle: compressor (green line), regenerator (blue line), receiver (brown line), combustor (grey line), turbine (cyan line), and exhaust gas (yellow line). Fig. 12b shows the power consumed by the compressor (green line), produced by the turbine (cyan line), the net power (difference between the power produced by the turbine and consumed by the compressor, red line), the solar power (yellow line), and fuel power (grey line). Their sum corresponds to the net power, and the power consumed by the MED-TVC unit (purple line), which is obtained from the exhaust gases and does not penalize the net produced power. Fig. 12c depicts the power over the receiver, which is received from the whole solar field. Fig. 12d shows the GOR (purple line) and distillate produced (blue line) by the MED-TVC unit. Finally, Fig. 12e shows the solar (orange line) and fuel (grey line) fractions, i.e., the percentage contribution to the net power.

As depicted in Fig. 12b, the total net power generated is significantly higher in summer, which is attributed to the increased availability of solar energy compared to winter. This trend is corroborated by the data on solar energy received (Fig. 12c) and the solar fraction available (Fig. 12e). Despite the system being equipped with a combustor, it alone cannot supply the full energy required for nominal operation. This limitation becomes evident at night during summer and on days without solar resources in winter, affecting both temperature (Fig. 12a) and power generation (Fig. 12b). Under such conditions, the turbine operates at 420 °C, producing a net power of 50 MW_e. Conversely, with sufficient solar energy, the turbine reaches its nominal operating temperature of 650 °C, generating 100 MW_e. This optimal performance is most common during daytime in summer due to the abundance of solar energy. Correspondingly, the distillate production (Fig. 12d) exhibits similar patterns. The MED-TVC system, utilizing the turbine's exhaust gases, achieves higher distillate outputs at elevated exhaust gas temperatures, which are attainable when solar energy is present, as the combustor alone is insufficient to maintain the turbine at nominal conditions. The GOR decreases instead, due mainly to a decrease in the latent heat of the motive steam leaving the steam generator (see Fig. 1) at higher exhaust gas temperatures. It leads to a higher thermal energy consumption to produce a greater amount of distillate. In other words, higher distillate production is achieved at a lower thermal efficiency, which is not important in this kind of schemes because waste heat that would otherwise be rejected to the environment is used to drive the desalination process producing an added value product like is the freshwater.

(a) Temperatures.

(b) Power consumed or produced by different elements in the system.

Fig. 12. (a-e) Simulation results for winter (1st – 10th February) and summer (7th – 13th July) weeks.

(c) Power over the solar receiver.

(d) MED-TVC GOR and distillate production.

Fig. 12. (continued).

(e) Fuel and solar fractions.

Fig. 12. (continued).

4. Conclusions

This study presents the development of a simulation tool designed to assess small-capacity solar thermal cogeneration plants using a central receiver and micro-gas turbine, coupled with a MED-TVC desalination unit. The system addresses two key challenges: water scarcity and sustainable energy production.

The case study, conducted for a coastal site in Cyprus, demonstrated that the tool can effectively simulate annual electricity and freshwater production. The results showed that during summer months, the system achieved 20 % higher electricity and freshwater outputs compared to winter months, with maximum solar fractions of 33 % in July. The solar fraction dropped to 11 % during winter, leading to increased reliance on the combustor for energy production. In terms of total freshwater production, the system generated 14,671 m³ annually, with the highest production occurring in July.

One of the findings is the system's ability to maintain power plant efficiency while utilizing exhaust heat for desalination. This allows for joint electricity and freshwater production without a reduction in the power cycle's performance. The simulation indicated that net electricity production varied seasonally, reaching a peak of 110 kW_e in July and dropping to a minimum of 38 kW_e during winter.

To enhance decarbonization, it is suggested that the system could benefit from the integration of energy storage technologies to increase solar share during low-irradiance periods.

Appendix A

Regression for the thermal vapor compression multi-effect distillation plant

The polynomial multi-variable regressions of the GOR and distillate production for the MED plant were obtained considering a second-degree polynomial according to the structure of the Eq. (A.1) and the inputs and range of variation mentioned in the corresponding section. The variables calculated were the freshwater mass flow rate (q_D , m³/d) and the Gain Output Ratio (GOR). The coefficients are presented in Table A1.

This work highlights the potential for small-scale renewable energy systems to address the dual challenges of sustainable power generation and water supply, particularly in off-grid or rural areas.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

J. Bonilla: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **B. Ortega-Delgado:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Formal analysis. **D.C. Alarcón-Padilla:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **J. Fernández-Reche:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **P. Palenzuela:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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$$\text{Variable} = a_1 p_{urb} + a_2 \dot{m}_g + a_3 \dot{m}_g p_{urb} + a_4 T_{exh} + a_5 T_{exh} p_{urb} + a_6 T_{exh} \dot{m}_g + a_7 + a_8 T_{exh}^2 + a_9 \dot{m}_g^2 + a_{10} p_{urb}^2 \tag{A1}$$

Table A1
Coefficients of the MED-TVC plant regression.

Variable Coefficients	GOR	q_D
1	-25.2514647	10.56190071
2	84.07910591	-214.6092961
3	32.70484913	-12.54692422
4	0.034455613	0.589033106
5	0.002619763	0.023338582
6	-0.18489816	0.275390807
7	-0.050509417	-0.857896799
8	8.49E-05	-0.001158311
9	-53.53690068	122.2401529
10	0.401066569	-3.604785419

The Normalized Root-Mean-Square Deviation (NRSMD) results are depicted in Table A.2.

Table A2
NRMSD of the outputs of the MED-TVC model.

Variable	NRMSD
Gain Output Ratio (GOR)	1.6 %
Distillate production (q_D)	2.1 %

Regression for the power consumption MED-TVC plant

The polynomial multi-variable regression of the power consumption of MED plant (SPC, kWh/m³) was obtained similarly to the GOR and q_D , mentioned previously. The inputs and range of variation mentioned in Section 4.3. The polynomial equations are presented below, and the coefficients are presented in Table A3, with a R² of 0.9474.

$$\text{SPC} = a_0 + a_1 \cdot T_a + a_2 \cdot q_a + a_3 \cdot p_a + a_4 \cdot T_a^2 + a_5 \cdot q_a^2 + a_6 \cdot p_a^2 + a_7 \cdot T_a \cdot q_a + a_8 \cdot T_a \cdot p_a + a_9 \cdot q_a \cdot p_a \tag{A2}$$

Table A3
Coefficients of the MED-TVC power consumption.

Coefficient a_i	Value
1	10.2164567
2	-0.06673876
3	2.70642086
4	2.00246803
5	9.8549E-05
6	-1.48728503
7	0.74368856
8	0.01410893
9	-0.00094474

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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